

SOCIAL SCIENCES

YOUTH DIGITAL MIGRATION INTO THE METAVERSE

Poghosyan G.,

Doctor, Professor of Sociology

*Institute of Philosophy, Sociology and Law of Armenian National
Academy of Sciences, Yerevan, Armenia*

Poghosyan R.

PhD in Psychology

*Institute of Philosophy, Sociology and Law
of Armenian National Academy of Sciences,
Yerevan, Armenia*

ABSTRACT

The impact of ongoing current digitalization and digital transformation of the society has also an influence on the migration processes and the new forms and types of migration. This is an area that needs to be studied for creating the relevant understanding of changings in social life. This article examines the new trends and difficulties that appear as the consequences of intervention of artificial intelligence in to the social life. The emergence of new forms of social activity and even new types of migration behavior, especially among the younger generation, raise the task of sociological research, in particular of such a new social phenomenon as the mass transition or digital migration of people into a metasociety. Currently, there is an active process of creation and emergence of a second reality in the virtual space of the Internet, in which digital duplicates or avatars of social network users created with the help of artificial intelligence can act as active actors. Modern sociologists are faced with the task of developing methods for studying the virtual behavior of backup avatars in the space of artificial reality, called metasociety.

Keywords: metaverse, migration, digital nomad, metasociety, avatar, parallel reality.

Introduction

Modern challenges and processes of digitalization of reality put forward the need to develop some new concepts in sociological theory. The challenges that exist within modern civilization have a nonlinear impact on all human life practices [Tiryakian E.A., 2014, 91-112]. This requires the development of fundamentally new types of modernization. The expansion of digitalization processes and the active intervention of artificial intelligence (AI) worries sociologists due to the complication of the dynamics of social development. A “pure” society no longer exists, and this, in essence, leads to the “end of the social” [Baudrillard, 1983]. Sociologists began to turn to interdisciplinary concepts that take into account modern trends in the nonlinearity and complexity of the new world order in the context of the growing process of digitalization. The hybridization of the social and material worlds leads to their “complete intertwining,” which contributes to the “alternativeness of future societies” and the multiplicity of variations. [Urry J. 2011, 8]. In this context, the new sociological theories are in demand, based on taking into account modern trends in the complexity and nonlinearity of the world order, the hybridization of socio-digital and natural reality, the development of artificial intelligence and the digital transformation of society.

Digital Migration

In the last few years, the new types of migration have appeared (in addition to the well-known traditional processes of immigration and emigration), which can change the concepts and ideas accepted in the sociological science. In this paper, we intend to present three such new migration types that expand our usual understanding.

Currently the global world has entered a new historical stage of a large-scale cold war. Today the world is moving towards a new world order, in which each country and unions of countries seek to reconsider their role and place in this process. Sociological studies showing the strong fragmentation of society in many countries. Tectonic changes occurring at the global level also have an impact on the public opinion.

With the start of war in Ukraine and Western sanctions toward Russian Federation, many Russians were forced to leave the country. In 2022, a fairly large flow of migrants from Russia to Armenia unexpectedly formed. The several tens of thousands of Russians moved to Armenia. The overwhelming majority of Russians who came to Armenia were representatives of medium-sized businesses engaged in the foreign economic activities. Some of them moved with entire offices. Thousands of Russian IT companies submitted applications to transfer their business².

²«If we get a job, we'll stay». <https://golosarmenii.am/article/143370/esli-poluchitsya-s-rabotoj--ostanemsya> (accessed:07.03.2023).

As a result of the relocation about 900 companies and about 4,000 small entrepreneurs were registered in Armenia by Russian citizens in 2023³. According to a Civilnet observer⁴, 50 thousand Russians entered Armenia in February-March 2022 alone. Some moved due to fear of political reprisals or conscription; others moved for economic reasons. They moved because working in Russia under sanctions became inconvenient for them; it was impossible to receive wages from abroad, use Western banking services, and not worry about food shortages and the closure of their favorite cafes and shops [Baktemir, 2022]. Residents of Armenian cities, who yesterday went to Russia for work, have become a priority direction of Russian migrants. At the same time, apartment rental prices have increased many times in the capital of Armenia. Many of our compatriots Armenians also chose to return and transfer their business to Armenia. By maintaining economic ties with Russia, they brought great benefits to the economies of both countries. [Poghosyan G.A., 2022]. The repatriation of Armenian migrants from Russia helped not only for modernization and investing in to Armenian economy, but also to improve the demographic situation.

This was a new form of migration, or non-traditional migration. Ordinary, traditional migration is, as a rule, a flow of people (labor migrants) looking for work or study in other countries. On a global scale, these are flows from poor countries of the South to prosperous Europe and the United States. Within the postsoviet space, these are flows of labor migrants, usually heading to Russia from the former Soviet republics. This is a fairly well-studied, traditional labor migration in the postsoviet space. However, what happened after the start of the war in Ukraine and strict sanctions against Russia was essentially a completely new, as yet little-studied form of migration. Sociologists called this non-traditional form of migration relocation, meaning the transfer of business, and the migrants called “relocants”.

Working in Remote Format

Sociological research in recent years has documented the transition from materialist to postmaterialist values. The first empirical evidence of intergenerational shifts was recorded in 1970 in Western European countries; the young people began to give preference to new goals - freedom of expression. They moved from the existential need to survive to the freedom of self-development and self-expression. [R. Ingelhard, 2018]. The process of socialization of youth involves a gradual change in values with the change of generations. In recent decades, the dominant values in highly developed societies have changed dramatically, transforming cultural norms that had previously been preserved for centuries. [R. Ingelhard, 2018].

Everyone remembers well how, due to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2019-2020, many transferred

their work to a remote format. This, of course, led to even greater fragmentation of society, to a sharp reduction in real social contacts between people. However, COVID soon passed, but remote work remained. And there will probably be even more in the future.

A new generation of young people has emerged, the so-called “digital generation”, for whom “remote” work has become a new way of life, the style of life for new generation. Since 1997, David Manners and Tsugio Makimoto have published the book “Digital Nomad” [Makimoto Ts., 1997]. According to this book, active digital travelers have replaced telecommuters and those who work from home.

The essence of the digital generation’s lifestyle is constant movement and expansion of one’s capabilities. Today, thanks to mobile communications and information technology, people are not tied to a specific place of work or study. The first wave of “digital nomads” consisted of programmers and IT specialists. Their favorite travel destinations are Bali in Indonesia, islands in Thailand and Goa in India. The most common professions among them are “e-commerce”, designers, marketers, copywriters, translators, data analysts, web developers, testing engineers, “big data” analysts and even accountants. The change of place of residence and the change of profession becomes for them a conscious step towards development, “improving a version of themselves.” They live in a world full of uncertainty, in which circumstances often change, and in which the boundaries of states are erased. They made the movement a model of their behavior, a new cult, a global trend [Beverly Y., 2019, 1-17].

Especially for this purpose, places for shared living and work, the so-called “coliving” and “coworking” spaces, have appeared in various countries. Something like cafes and hotels, but with a different content. The usual offices and noisy cafes with poor Internet access have been replaced by “coworking spaces.” And “coliving” spaces have become hostels of interest to digital nomads from all over the world.

“Digital nomadism” actually represents another non-traditional form or new type of migration. Compared to the first form of non-traditional migration – relocation, the “digital nomadism” is “migration in reverse”. In other words, “digital nomads” are mainly highly qualified specialists who prefer to work in their own company, but not in the office of this company, but with a free schedule, at a great distance from the office, with the opportunity to travel around the world, to different countries, without taking time off from work. In the case of relocations, we are dealing with the physical transfer of a business and even office employees to another country, with a more favorable economic and political climate for their business. While “digital nomads,” on the contrary, maintaining work in their office, in their own country, prefer to work remotely, traveling around the world.

³ Alikan Telnov. 2022. Trouble comes quietly. (In Russ.) https://golosarmenii.am/article/213243/beda-prixoditixo?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMTEAAR1A2-68AuCAmBh53xjpd-bRXz23CAgNkQLQaKU65Rs4ThyyfTIbcm-GIMqs_aem_orNHuyQH22mGsa5Z7IKxTw

⁴ Is Yerevan the new Amsterdam? About the influx of Russians to Armenia // Civilnet. 2022. 12.03. URL: <https://www.civilnet.am/ru/news/653451/ереван-новый-амстердам-о-притоке-россиян-в-армению/> (accessed: 15.08. 2024). (In Russ.)

Migration to Metasociety

By the experts in 5-10 years, AI will create such an extensive virtual reality that it will be difficult to distinguish it from the real one. Over the years, there has been an interpenetration of two realities, a kind of interference between virtual and real realities. In the same way, AI plots can be both a real and far-fetched, so artificial that they are difficult to distinguish. Describing the postmodern model of society, J. Baudrillard used the term “hyperreality”. He describes a state in which a person cannot distinguish reality from simulation, since all objects of the physical world are replaced by images and signs, which he called “simulacra.” [Baudrillard, Jean, 1981].

Now AI is being trained to imitate people, make films, give interviews on behalf of another person and in his voice. New models of ChatGPT versions will have the ability to influence people, penetrate social networks and manipulate public opinion. Artificial intelligence will be able to create hundreds of thousands of humanoid bots that will influence mass consciousness.

From a sociological point of view, AI is interesting because it makes obvious the problems of the development of artificial sociality. Technologies such as ChatGPT open up new, previously unpredictable opportunities to transform human dependence on algorithms. [Lindberg S., 2023, 140]. Today there are modernized and improved AI models that are 50 times smarter than the older versions. They perform natural language processing, search engine optimization, image and video processing, augmented reality and virtual reality. Now researchers are talking about creating the next generation of Internet platforms, which is called the “metaverse”. [Ball, 2020]. Meta founder Mark Zuckerberg described the world of the metaverse as “the internet where you are, not just looking at it.”⁵ The goal of the metaverse is to create new ways of interaction between people and the digitalization of real life. In the world of the metaverse there is no single matrix; it is a reality in which space is created by the users themselves. By February 2022, more than 10,000 virtual worlds had already been built. The number of monthly active users has already exceeded several hundred thousand people. By 2026, one in four of us will spend at least an hour a day in the metaverse: working, studying, socializing and making necessary purchases [Ball, 2020]. However, recent sociological studies have shown that today students have increased the amount of time spent on the Internet several times: in 2023, 83% of students spent more than 4 hours a day, and for some this figure reached 10 hours [Lesnykh, 2023, 62]. Essentially, this is a new virtual reality, an artificially created space in which real life is gradually transferred to a digital platform. Thus, metasociety is gradually beginning to displace the real sociality, digitizing many forms of human activity.

Now large shopping centers and malls have begun to experience difficulties with customers, because

young people are gradually moving to online shopping platforms with home delivery. They order not only food, but also clothes, shoes, equipment and everything else. Online trading is actively replacing trade in large stores and shopping centers. Online trading platforms will dominate in the near future. Visiting museums in other countries and cities becomes available online. To do this, you don't need to go to another country, buy a ticket, or stand in a long line to get into museums, theaters and exhibitions. Digital tourism will become accessible to many people, and for many will replace expensive trips abroad. Online tourism in many cases can replace real travel. The international scientific community widely uses the opportunity to participate in scientific conferences online. A huge number of scientists had the opportunity to give reports and papers at scientific conferences. Previously, such active and broad participation was simply impossible due to high travel costs. The same can be said for the new online learning opportunity. Many reputable universities have made themselves accessible to a huge number of students through online portals.

Avatars in Metasociety

Digital migrants or digital autistics of our time prefer a kind of “escape from reality” into a second, parallel reality. We are witnessing a historical transition into a metasociety. A second, parallel life creates the possibility of a double life in virtual reality on the World Wide Web. Digital relocation allows people to escape “without loss” to another reality, to a new “other world.” This is an artificial parallel life in another reality. Each digital migrant will soon have its own artificial intelligence in digital reality or a kind of digital avatar in the metasociety. This is an example of living in a parallel reality with your personal avatar. An avatar that can continue to live in a metasociety, even after the actual death of a person in the real life.

Meta (former Facebook) has created photorealistic 3D avatars that are designed to replace the usual avatars in social networks and applications. The development makes it possible to convey the user's appearance so accurately that the 3D avatar becomes indistinguishable from a living person. 3D avatars, also known as digital doubles, will inhabit the metaverse the company is creating. The Horizon Home social network will allow you to meet friends, not physical ones, but in the form of avatars in a virtual space created on the platform. People will be able to stay in the metaverse longer, practically without interfering with reality. Mark Zuckerberg even coins the term “friends from different layers of reality.”⁶ He believes that the metaverse is simply a digital space where humans have existed for a long time. In fact, the transition of humanity to digital reality has already occurred. Meta company strives to create the so-called mixed reality, when physical objects can be placed in a digital environment and vice versa - virtual objects or people in the form of holograms come to life next to us.

⁵ Into the metaverse: What is it? <https://engati.medium.com/into-the-metaverse-what-is-it-960a22c6cea3> (accessed: 12.10.2024)

⁶ Avatar in the metaverse: risks of using digital twins. <https://telesputnik.ru/materials/hipe/article/avatar-v-metavselennoy-riski-ispolzovaniya-tsifrovyykh-dvoynikov-> (accessed: 23.08.2024). (In Russ.)

In 2023 the columnist of “Wall Street Journal” Joanna Stern tried to find out how real and how human-like can a digital avatar created by artificial intelligence be and can it fool the real people. Using the “Synthesia” tool, she created her virtual avatar. “According to the developers, this tool can create video avatars based on video and audio recordings of real people”⁷. The result was more frightening than she could have imagined. Once the avatar was ready, “Joanna created text for a TikTok video about iOS using ChatGPT and uploaded it to her avatar” and created the final video. When Joanna watched the video, she thought she saw her reflection in the mirror. Her voice clone was created with ElevenLabs' generative AI algorithm. This audio avatar can reproduce any text with the voice of user. Joanna tested this voice clone, which turned out that audio clone is more like a real person than the video clone⁸.

Recently the Chinese “Tencent Cloud” announced the launch of a digital platform for creating people Deepfakes-as-a-Service (DFaaS). It promises to create high-definition digital copies for everyone, using just three minutes of live video and 100 spoken phrases.⁹ By the Harvard Crimson newspaper “CS50 will integrate artificial intelligence (AI) into course instruction”. CS50 professor David J. Malan '99 wrote “Through AI, we hope to reduce that time spent, so as to reallocate TFs' time toward more meaningful, interpersonal time with their students, akin to an apprenticeship model”.¹⁰ In the next 10 years, people will live on neural networks. AI is quickly entering our lives and becoming an integral part of many professions: from (SMM) Social Media Manager and computer designers to doctors. Many people are already mastering intensive AI courses, basic skills in working with ChatGPT, DALL-E 3, Midjourney, Runway, HeyGen, Invideo. Recently Sam Altman¹¹, the creator OpenAI, has said that he believes we will achieve artificial general intelligence, also known as superintelligence (AGI) in 2025 with the release of the first AI agents joining the workforce.

Conclusion

Sociology today is becoming more and more in demand, and in the near future it will become simply necessary in a rapidly changing society. Before our eyes, historical transformations are taking place in the life of familiar society. The current generation of sociologists will have to explore and understand the meaning of the fundamental changes associated with the emergence of a second or virtual reality. It is already obvious today that an increasing number of young people spend several hours of their time every day on the Internet and in social networks.

Sociologists predict in the near future a significant expansion of the types of life activities carried out by young people within the framework of this parallel artificial reality, called “metasociety”. The further development of generative AI will greatly increase the transfer or duplication of human activity into the space of metasociety. This is another new form of migration - the transfer of various types of activities from the space of familiar reality to the space of virtual, parallel or artificial reality; this is a migration outflow into a parallel reality. Moreover, in the near future, various activities in this artificial reality will be autonomously carried out by human backups - digital avatars - created specifically for this purpose with the help of AI. The creators of AI are already predicting the emergence of digital analogues of humans, or personal digital avatars, which can easily replace many of our activities in the metasociety without our direct participation.

Thus, sociologists are faced with the full task of scientifically studying this second reality or metasociety in all its details, challenges and risks for our usual way of life. It seems that this will require the creation of a new, digital sociology capable of studying and solving unusual problems of metasociety.

References

1. Baktemir T. 2022. Unreal foreign country // Cold. 2022.19.03. (In Russ.) URL: <https://holod.media/2022/03/19/nenastoyashhaya-zagranicza/> (accessed:12.04.2022).
2. Inglehart R. 2018. Cultural evolution: how human motivations change and how it changes the world. M.: Mysl, p. 40. (In Russ.)
3. Lesnykh E.A. 2023. The Internet as a destructive “time trap” // Spiritual security and traditionalism: selected materials of the international scientific and educational conference / resp. ed. A.G. Polyakov. Kirov: «VESI» LLC. P. 60-64. (In Russ.)
4. Poghosyan G.A. Interview «Emigration vs Repatriation: why do people leave and under what conditions are they ready to return?» https://www.golosarmanii.am/article/141618/emigraciya-VS-repatriaciya-pochemu-lyudi-uezzhayut-i-pri-kakix-usloviyax-gotovy-vernutsya?fbclid=IwAR29fYNEChzsWbY7PGGKUWqs aodf04KcPo7v2agJjNBmaWeDL0m_r3mRrvA (accessed: 16.02.2024). (In Russ.)
5. Ball M. 2020. The Metaverse: What It Is, Where to Find it, and Who Will Build It. Jan 13. <https://www.matthewball.vc/all/themetaverse> (accessed: 10.07.2023).
6. Baudrillard, Jean, 1981. Simulacres et simulation. Paris: Galilée.

⁷ How real can a virtual avatar be? It bypassed the bank's protection and fooled real people. <https://tech.news.am/eng/news/1247/how-real-can-a-virtual-avatar-be-it-bypassed-the-banks-protection-and-fooled-real-people.html> (accessed: 11.01.2025).

⁸ How real can a virtual avatar be? It bypassed the bank's protection and fooled real people. <https://tech.news.am/eng/news/1247/how-real-can-a-virtual-avatar-be-it-bypassed-the-banks-protection-and-fooled-real-people.html> (accessed: 12.10.2024).

⁹ Sergey Petrenko. AI is capable of creating a digital avatar of a person that can mislead both relatives and the bank. <https://rg.ru/2023/05/10/cifrovaia-kopiia-cheloveka-obman-ula-bank.html> (accessed: 14.09.2024). (In Russ.)

¹⁰ <https://www.thecrimson.com/article/2023/6/21/cs50-artificial-intelligence/> (accessed: 05.10.2024).

¹¹ <https://www.techradar.com/computing/artificial-intelligence/sam-altman-predicts-artificial-superintelligence-agi-will-happen-this-year> (accessed: 05.01. 2025).

7. Baudrillard, Jean. 1983. *In the Shadow of the Silent Majorities, Or, the End of the Social and other Essays*. Semiotext(e), Columbia University, New York.
8. Beverly Y. Thompson. 2019. *The Digital Nomad Lifestyle: (Remote) Work/Leisure Balance, Privilege, and Constructed Community* // *International Journal of the Sociology of Leisure*. March. P. 1-17. doi.org/10.1007/s41978-018-00030-y <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329776443>
9. Lindberg S. 2023. *From Technological Humanity to Bio-technical Existence*. State University of New York. 140 p.
10. Makimoto Ts., Manners D. 1997. *Digital Nomad,* Wiley, 256 p.
11. Tiryakian E.A. 2014. *Civilization in the global era: one, many... or none?* // *Social theory and regional studies in the global age* / ed. by S. Aijomand. New York: SUNY press. P. 91-112.
12. Urry J. 2011. *Climate change and society*. Cambridge: Polity. 217 p.